

TABLE—6

No.	5-Substituent	m.p.°C	Yield %	Mol. Formula
1.	Phenyl	190	57	C ₂₀ H ₂₁ N ₃ S
2.	4-Tolyl	206	52	C ₂₁ H ₂₃ N ₃ S
3.	4-Chlorophenyl	234	55	C ₂₀ H ₂₀ N ₃ SCl

Note : All melting points are uncorrected.
All the compounds on analysis were found to correspond with the required values

Acknowledgement

Thanks to Ciba-Geigy Research Centre, Bombay, for all spectral and elemental analyses.

References

1. L. KNORR and A. BLANK, *Ber.*, 1885, 18, 316.
2. E. FISCHER and E. KNOVENAGEL, *Ann.*, 1877, 239, 194.
3. V. AUWERS, K. and VOSS *Ber.*, 1909 42 411.
4. S. VIEBEL, *Acta Chim, Scand.*, 1947, 1, 54.

Chemical Investigation of Some Mangrove Species : Part VI : *Sonneratia apetala*

S. GHOSH MAJUMDAR and GOURI PATRA

Department of Chemistry, The University of Burdwan,
Burdwan 713 104

Manuscript received 5 May 1978, revised 14 August 1978,
accepted 6 September 1978

LITERATURE survey¹⁻⁶ on the genus *Sonneratia* (Fam. Sonneratiaceae) reveals the presence of ellagic acid and its methyl ester ; anthraquinonoids derivatives ; gibberellin from its five species and ursolic acid and β -sitosterol from *S. apetala*. The present report on *S. apetala* from Sunderban area (Lat. 16° NH) and Kakinada area (Lat. 20° NH) is mainly intended to determine the ecological influence upon the plant on its secondary metabolites. The analysis confirms the presence of ursolic acid and β -sitosterol (in abundance) together with β -amyrin and taraxerol (in traces) in all the investigated species which were systematically collected in the month of December.

The finely powdered bark of *S. apetala* (7.0 Kg) from Sunderban area was extracted with petroleum for 30 hrs. The ether soluble portion of the extract was then separated into neutral and acidic fraction. The neutral fraction consisted of the following compounds (by column chromatography).

The first fraction, petroleum benzene eluate (5.0 lit., 7 : 3) yielded triacontanol m. p. 80° (0.25g)

Second fraction had m. p. 260° which on repeated crystallisation from benzene-ethanol mixture furnished a white crystalline compound (0.02g) m.p. 268°. The identity of this compound with that of taraxerol has been confirmed through mixed m.p., tlc., co-GLC study (Ret time ; 17 : 7 mins at 250-256.5°. Column material : 3% SE 30 on gas chrome-Z, 60-80 mesh).

Third fraction (benzene eluate, 3.0 lit.) furnished a mixture which was separated through fractional crystallisation from benzene-ethanol. The pure compound was identified as β -amyrin by mixed m.p. 195° and super impossible IR spectrum : $\nu_{\max}$ 3250 (hydroxyl), 1775 (double bond), 1450 and 1350 (gem dimethyl) cm⁻¹.

The last fraction contain large amount of β -sitosterol (3 g) m.p. 135° from benzene-chloroform (1 : 1) eluate.

Acidic fraction (8.0 g) of each extract was esterified with ethereal solution of diazomethane. The crude ester (14.0 g) on chromatography over silica gel G (750 g) yielded a triterpenic ester which on repeated crystallisation from aqueous ethanol (80%) furnished homogeneous shining crystals (6.0 g) m.p. 110°. $[\alpha]_D +520$, $\nu_{\max}$ 3300 (-OH), 1720 (carbonyl), 1640 and 790 cm⁻¹ (double bond), derivative. Uvaol (LiAlH₄ reduced product of methyl ester) m.p. 218°. All these data confirmed the identity at the methyl ester with methyl ursolate.

S. apetala from Kakinada showed identical result.

Acknowledgement

The authors are highly indebted to Mr. Asit Baran Sinha of the Department of Chemistry, Burdwan University for constant help during the whole programme of the present investigation.

References

1. G. P. CHOUDHURY, V. N. SHARMA and S. SIDDIQUI, *J. Sci. Ind. Res. (India)*, 1960, 19B, 142.
2. S. N. SRIVASTAVA, D. S. BHAKUNI, V. N. SARMA and K. N. KAUL, *J. Sci. Ind. Res. (India)*, 1962, 21B, 549.
3. S. N. GANGULY, T. SANYAL, P. K. SARKAR and S. M. SIRCAR, *Chem. & Indust. (London)*, 1972, 10, 424.
4. P. GASKIN, J. MACMILLAN, S. N. GANGULY, T. SANYAL, P. K. SARKAR and S. M. SIRCAR, *Chem. & Indust. (London)*, 1972, 10, 424.
5. J. B. LOWRY, *Phytochemistry*, 1968, 7 1803.
6. Review in D. Phil dissertation (1976) of Mrs. G. PATRA admitted by The University of Burdwan.